

CLASS SCHEDULE AND LEARNING PERFORMANCE OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION SUBJECTS IN SENATOR NINOY AQUINO

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ABSTRACT

Time matters in shaping students' learning. This explores how class schedule impacts Junior High School students' performance in Physical Education. Class schedules play a crucial role in shaping learners' academic performance, particularly in subjects that require active engagement like Physical Education (PE). This study examined the influence of class schedules on the learning performance of junior high school students in Physical Education (PE) across five secondary schools in Senator Ninoy Aquino, Sultan Kudarat. Using a stratified sampling technique, data were collected through surveys and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics using t-test. Results revealed that PE class schedules were rated as excellent in terms of structure and acceptability. Intrinsic learning performance showed significant differences, with morning class learners demonstrating higher interest, study habits, perceived competence, and perceived choice. Extrinsic learning performance, including performance goals and challenge mastery, showed no significant differences between morning and afternoon sessions. Quarterly assessments also indicated that both groups performed excellently, with no significant difference in overall academic outcomes. The findings suggest that morning classes may provide a more favorable learning environment due to higher motivation and cognitive engagement, likely influenced by sleep habits and circadian rhythms. Extrinsic motivation remained stable across both schedules, emphasizing the importance of effective teaching strategies. Based on these findings, it is recommended that schools maintain well-structured and highly acceptable PE schedules while exploring flexible scheduling options to support individual learning preferences. Strategies should be implemented to enhance intrinsic motivation,

particularly in afternoon classes, by incorporating engaging and student-centered activities

Keywords: *Class Schedule, Intrinsic Motivation, Extrinsic Motivation, Learning Performance, Academic Outcomes*

INTRODUCTION

Students' learning is a crucial aspect of education, as it reflects their academic achievements and mastery of subject matter. It is primarily measured by students' ability to understand instructions, engage actively in activities, and demonstrate knowledge through assessments and evaluations. An effective learning environment fosters constructive development, inclusivity, and support. The scheduling of physical education (PE) subjects in junior high school is a critical factor influencing learning outcomes.

Various international studies indicate that class scheduling significantly impacts students' learning performance, with Laar et al. (2021) emphasizing the need for innovative scheduling and teaching methods to maintain engagement, especially in an era of technological integration. In physical education (PE), scheduling plays a crucial role in participation, responses, and performance, as Silva et al. (2021) highlights its benefits in promoting health-related behaviors, improving motor skills, and enhancing competence. Whereas inconsistencies in school scheduling, particularly in the United States, have led to the de-prioritization of PE, as many schools prioritize other subjects. Murawski et al. (2021) emphasize structured PE scheduling to foster both intrinsic and extrinsic engagement.

In the Philippines, The National Secondary Achievement Test (NSAT) and PISA 2018 results highlight significant gaps in student performance in the Philippines, particularly in science and mathematics, with Filipino learners ranking second to last in science literacy among 78 countries. Research by Jongko et al. (2024) in Cebu City emphasizes that well-structured learning objectives and resource utilization in MAPEH enhance student engagement and performance, yet inconsistencies in school scheduling often deprioritize Physical Education (PE), limiting its benefits.

In the schools of Senator Ninoy Aquino, one of the pressing local issues affecting junior high school students' learning performance in Physical Education (PE) is the inconsistent scheduling and limited time allocation for PE classes. Many schools tend to prioritize academic subjects such as Mathematics, Science, and English, leading to the reduction or rescheduling of PE sessions. This issue results in decreased student engagement, lower physical activity levels, and missed opportunities for skill development. The lack of proper facilities and resources further hampers the effective implementation of PE programs. The NSAT results highlight the need to strengthen MAPEH subjects, including PE, to address educational gaps and promote holistic student development (Jongko et al., 2024). Without a well-structured class schedule, learners

struggle to meet the expected learning outcomes in PE, affecting their overall physical fitness, discipline, and well-being.

In local settings such as Senator Ninoy Aquino. Most studies focus on core academic subjects, while research on the scheduling and structuring of PE classes remains limited. Despite extensive research on the influence of class schedules on academic performance, there remains a gap which already registered, or knowledge needs updates for improvements or remodeling and redesigning for better results. This study aims to bridge this research gap by investigating the direct relationship between class scheduling and learning performance in junior high school PE classes in Senator Ninoy Aquino, providing insights into potential improvements in curriculum planning and implementation.

Given the crucial role of PE in students' cognitive, physical, and emotional development, addressing the issue of class scheduling in Senator Ninoy Aquino schools is urgent. This study is urgent because in today's fast paced educational environment, optimizing students' performance in Physical Education (PE) is more critical than ever despite its vital role in physical health, mental well-being, and over all academic success. If PE is scheduled at the wrong time, students may feel less motivated, less engaged, and perform poorly. This study is urgent because it helps schools find the best schedule to keep students active, motivated, and performing at their best.

Research Questions

This research generally aimed to examine motivational factors and determine the level of performance of coaches in Sultan Kudarat Province.

Specifically, this sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of the quality of class schedule of the respondents in Physical Education in terms of:
 - a. schedule, and
 - b. acceptability?
2. What is the level of intrinsic learning performance of the respondents in morning class and afternoon class Physical Education in terms of:
 - a. interest;
 - b. study habits;
 - c. perceived competence, and
 - d. perceived choice?
3. What is the level of extrinsic learning performance of the respondents in morning class and afternoon class Physical Education in terms of:
 - a. performance goal, and
 - b. challenge mastery?
4. What is the level of learning performance of the students in terms of quarterly assessment?
5. Is there a significant difference between morning and afternoon class intrinsic learning performance in Physical Education subjects of the respondents?

6. Is there a significant difference between morning and afternoon class extrinsic learning performance in Physical Education subjects of the respondents?
7. Is there a significant difference between class schedule and learning performance of the respondents?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to investigate the influence of class schedules on the learning performance of junior high school students in Physical Education within Senator Ninoy Aquino, Sultan Kudarat. Using stratified and snowball sampling, there were 175 Grade 10 students from five public high schools were selected to participate. The study utilized both adopted and researcher-made survey questionnaires, validated through pilot testing with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.87, to assess the quality and acceptability of class schedules as well as students' intrinsic and extrinsic learning performance. Data were gathered using a five-point Likert Scale and analyzed using t-tests, means, and standard deviations. The results aimed to identify patterns and relationships between class schedules (morning vs. afternoon) and student performance in PE without random assignment, addressing real-world conditions and practical constraints of educational settings. The findings are expected to inform teaching strategies, improve physical education delivery, and guide future policymaking in similar contexts.

RESULTS

Table 1. Level of Quality of Class Schedule

Statement	Mean	SD	Description
Schedule	4.80	0.45	Excellent
Acceptability	4.86	0.28	Excellent

Table 2. Level of Intrinsic Learning Performance

Indicators	Morning			Afternoon		
	Mean	SD	Description	Mean	SD	Description
Interest	3.84	0.68	High	3.55	0.67	High
Study Habits	3.56	0.68	High	3.41	0.54	High
Perceived Competence	3.60	0.67	High	3.48	0.63	High
Perceived Choice	3.49	0.68	High	3.35	0.59	High

Table 3. The level of Extrinsic Learning Performance

Indicators	Morning			Afternoon		
	Mean	SD	Description	Mean	SD	Description
Performance Goal	3.47	0.69	High	3.40	0.62	Moderate
Challenge Mastery	3.65	0.69	High	3.55	0.69	High

Table 4. Level of Learning Performance in Quarterly Assessment.

Quarterly Assessment	AM	PM
Mean	84.82	86.00
SD	5.32	4.81

Table 5. Analysis of the Morning and Afternoon Class Intrinsic Learning Performance in Physical Education Subjects of the Respondents.

	Interest		Study Habits		Perceived Competence		Perceived Choice		Overall Intrinsic	
	AM	PM	AM	PM	AM	PM	AM	PM	AM	PM
Mean	3.84	3.55	3.56	3.41	3.60	3.48	3.49	3.35	3.62	3.45
SD	0.68	0.67	0.68	0.54	0.67	0.63	0.68	0.59	0.59	0.49
Mean Difference	0.29		0.14		0.12		0.14		0.17	
p-value	0.01		0.14		0.25		0.17		0.04	
	Significant		No Significant		No Significant		No Significant		Significant	

Table 6. Analysis of the Morning and Afternoon Class Extrinsic Learning Performance in Physical Education Subjects of the Respondents.

	Performance Goal		Challenge Mastery		Overall intrinsic	
	AM	PM	AM	AM	PM	AM
Mean	3.47	3.40	3.65	3.47	3.40	3.65
SD	0.69	0.62	0.69	0.69	0.62	0.69
Mean Difference	0.08		0.11		0.09	
p-value	0.46		0.32		0.33	
	No Significant		No Significant		No Significant	

Table 7. Analysis of Class Schedule and Learning Performance

	AM	PM
Mean	84.82	86.00
SD	5.32	4.81
Mean Difference		1.18
p-value		0.13
		No Significant

DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the level of quality of the class schedule, with both the overall schedule and its acceptability receiving excellent ratings. The schedule has an overall mean of 4.80 and a standard deviation of 0.45, interpreted as excellent, reflecting a strong positive perception of its structure and effectiveness. The acceptability of the class schedule has an overall mean of 4.86 and a standard deviation of 0.28, also categorized as excellent, suggesting a high level of satisfaction with the schedule's design and implementation.

The results from Table 1 align with existing literature on the importance of well-structured Physical Education (PE) schedules in promoting student engagement and satisfaction. The high overall mean scores for both the schedule and its acceptability, reflecting an "excellent" rating, indicate a positive perception of the PE schedule, particularly in its alignment with curriculum goals, clarity, and structure. This supports Murawski et al. (2021), who emphasized that well-planned PE schedules enhance student readiness and engagement, and Ryu et al. (2020), who found that structured scheduling increases physical activity levels.

Table 2 presents the level of intrinsic learning performance among learners in morning and afternoon Physical Education classes, revealing that both groups exhibit a high level of intrinsic motivation across the four indicators: interest, study habits, perceived competence, and perceived choice. In morning classes, the highest mean score is in interest with a mean of 3.84, followed by perceived competence with a mean of 3.60, study habits with a mean of 3.56, and perceived choice with a mean of 3.49, indicating that learners tend to show greater enthusiasm, confidence, and engagement during morning sessions. Meanwhile, afternoon classes also show high levels of performance, although with slightly lower mean scores. Interest has a mean of 3.55, followed by perceived competence at 3.48, study habits at 3.41, and perceived choice at 3.35. These findings suggest that while both schedules promote strong intrinsic learning performance, learners in morning classes generally display slightly higher levels of interest, motivation, and self-perceived ability, implying that the time of day may influence students' engagement and motivation in Physical Education.

The findings from Table 2 align with existing research on factors influencing learners' engagement and intrinsic motivation in Physical Education (PE) classes, particularly regarding the influence of class timing on various performance indicators. The

higher scores in morning classes for interest, study habits, perceived competence, and perceived choice support studies by Sağın (2022), which emphasize the role of a supportive learning environment and constructive feedback in enhancing student motivation. The decline in engagement and study habits in afternoon classes, as reflected by slightly lower mean scores, correlates with research by Bai (2023), which suggest that fatigue and stress can diminish student involvement in PE activities.

Table 3 presents the level of extrinsic learning performance among learners in morning and afternoon Physical Education (PE) classes. The data shows that for the performance goal indicator, morning learners have a high mean score of 3.47 with a standard deviation of 0.69, while afternoon learners show a slightly lower mean score of 3.40 and a standard deviation of 0.62, categorizing their performance as moderate. This suggests that learners in the morning classes tend to have a stronger external motivation to achieve specific goals compared to those in the afternoon.

The findings from Table 3 align with existing research on the role of extrinsic motivation and the impact of class timing on learners' performance in Physical Education (PE). The higher performance goal scores in morning classes suggest that morning learners may be more driven by external goals such as achieving high grades, which supports studies highlighting that performance-approach goals can enhance persistence and effort in PE (Ağbuğa et al., 2015). This may be due to factors such as higher cognitive alertness and better readiness to engage in the morning, as indicated by previous studies (Lucena et al., 2018).

Table 4 presents the level of learning performance in terms of quarterly assessment, showing a slight variation between morning and afternoon classes. The morning class learners have a mean score of 84.82 with a standard deviation of 5.32, while the afternoon class learners have a slightly higher mean score of 86.00 with a standard deviation of 4.81. These results suggest that afternoon learners, on average, performed marginally better in their quarterly assessments than their morning counterparts. The standard deviation values indicate that the scores in the morning class are slightly more dispersed, whereas the afternoon class shows more consistent performance among learners.

Table 5 presents the analysis of intrinsic learning performance in Physical Education using a t-test to compare morning and afternoon classes across four dimensions: interest, study habits, perceived competence, and perceived choice. Morning class learners had a higher overall intrinsic learning performance mean (3.62) compared to afternoon class learners (3.45), with the highest mean difference observed in interest (0.29), followed by study habits (0.14), perceived choice (0.14), and perceived competence (0.12). Statistical analysis revealed that only the difference in interest was significant ($p = 0.01$), indicating that morning learners had a significantly higher interest in PE, while differences in study habits ($p = 0.14$), perceived competence ($p = 0.25$), and perceived choice ($p = 0.17$) were not statistically significant.

The interest level of junior high school students plays a crucial role in their learning performance. A significant difference in intrinsic outcomes was observed between morning and afternoon PE classes, highlighting the impact of interest on student engagement. Research suggests that students' interest in learning is closely linked to their academic performance, with higher interest levels fostering greater engagement and participation in educational activities (Wiradarma et al., 2021). This idea is further supported by studies emphasizing that interest serves as a critical precursor to performance, particularly in less structured learning environments. When students are genuinely interested in a subject, their intrinsic motivation increases, leading to better academic outcomes. Fostering an engaging learning environment—through technology, effective pedagogical strategies, and meaningful feedback—can enhance students' motivation and interest (Wong & Wong, 2019).

Table 6 presents the analysis of extrinsic learning performance in Physical Education using a t-test to compare morning and afternoon classes across two dimensions: performance goal and challenge mastery. Morning learners had a slightly higher overall extrinsic learning performance mean (3.65) than afternoon learners (3.40), with a mean difference of 0.08 for performance goal and 0.11 for challenge mastery. However, statistical analysis revealed that none of these differences were significant, as the p-values for performance goal (0.46), challenge mastery (0.32), and overall extrinsic learning performance (0.33) exceeded the significance threshold. These findings suggest that while morning learners showed marginally higher extrinsic learning performance, the time of day does not substantially impact learners' motivation to achieve external goals or overcome challenges in Physical Education.

The findings affirm that the extrinsic performance of morning and afternoon PE classes is comparable. This uniformity in performance outcomes can be attributed to the teaching methodologies employed in PE classes. The Game Modification Approach, as noted by Khairuddin et al. (2023), enhances student enjoyment and engagement, leading to improved physical fitness and motivation. Its effectiveness in both morning and afternoon sessions helps neutralize potential time-of-day effects on performance.

Table 7 presents the analysis of the significant difference between class schedule and learning performance in Physical Education, as measured through quarterly assessments. Results indicate that afternoon learners had a slightly higher mean score (86.00) than morning learners (84.82), with a mean difference of 1.18. However, statistical analysis showed that this difference was not significant ($p = 0.13$), suggesting that the learners' class schedule—whether morning or afternoon—does not have a statistically significant impact on their learning performance in Physical Education.

Studies on physical activity and cognition suggest that while morning exercise may offer benefits, overall cognitive performance remains consistent across different times of the day. Vinne et al. (2014) found that late chronotypes performed poorly only in morning exams but showed no significant difference in afternoon tests, indicating that time of day may not be a critical factor for all learners.

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn based on the findings of the study.

The physical education (PE) class schedules at the five secondary schools in Senator Ninoy Aquino have been assessed as excellent and highly acceptable, suggesting that their structure and timing effectively meet educational standards and student needs. Research indicates a significant difference in the intrinsic learning performance of junior high students in PE based on whether they attend morning or afternoon sessions. Morning classes tend to create a more favorable learning environment, where students demonstrate higher levels of motivation and cognitive functioning, leading to increased engagement and responsiveness. This enhanced mental alertness is likely due to students' healthier sleep habits, such as going to bed earlier, which positively affects their readiness to learn. The timing of PE classes significantly influences students' motivation and performance, with morning sessions typically resulting in improved academic outcomes. Factors such as circadian rhythms and effective teaching strategies that promote student autonomy further contribute to heightened engagement and ownership of learning.

While no significant differences were found in terms of study habits, perceived competence, and perceived choice between morning and afternoon sessions, it suggests that these internal motivators are consistently fostered across both groups. Furthermore, there were no significant differences in the level of learning performance based on quarterly assessments, nor in extrinsic learning performance, indicating that external motivators such as rewards are similarly effective for both groups. However, a significant difference was observed in overall intrinsic learning performance, suggesting that internal factors like interest, study habits, perceived choice, and perceived competence influence students' engagement in both morning and afternoon sessions. Overall, there was no significant difference between class schedule and learning performance, with individual factors like attendance, active participation in extracurricular activities, and personal talents playing a crucial role in shaping student performance. These findings emphasize the importance of a well-rounded educational experience beyond the classroom.

Recommendations

From the salient findings of this study and the conclusion reached, the following recommendations are presented.

1. School administrators may conduct periodic assessments of the Physical Education (PE) class schedule to ensure that it aligns with learners' preferences and learning efficiency.
2. Teacher may integrate engaging and interactive activities in PE classes to sustain learners' interest, such as gamified learning, real-world applications, and student-centered teaching strategies.
3. PE teachers may establish clear and attainable learning goals that motivate learners to achieve specific performance benchmarks.

4. Teachers may optimizing learning performance in quarterly assessments, schools should integrate diverse assessment strategies, including formative assessments, skill-based evaluations, and performance tasks, to provide a more holistic measure of learners' progress.
5. Teachers may implement tailored teaching strategies that accommodate the cognitive and physical readiness of morning and afternoon learners.
6. Schools may adopt flexible instructional strategies that maintain motivation and engagement across different schedules.
7. School administrators may explore scheduling adjustments that optimize learning performance, such as balancing morning and afternoon class sizes to ensure equitable learning conditions.
8. Future studies may further investigate the impact of class schedules on cognitive and physical performance in PE to provide evidence-based recommendations for improving scheduling practices.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author affirms that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study. Ethical approval was obtained before the commencement of the research, and informed consent was acquired from all respondents involved. No specific funding was received for this research from any public, commercial, or not-for-profit organizations. The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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